

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D2.5.2 “ Porous sorbents from biomasses valorization”

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M8 to M 30
Periodic report date and version:	29-09-2025
Deliverable # Responsible	UPO Disit (Marchese -Bisio-Boccaleri)
RM2 Responsible	Arlorio

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

List of Deliverables

List of Deliverables

D. No	Name	Type	Disseminati on Level	Due Date	Delivery Date (actual)
[number]	[name]	[R — Document, report] [DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA — data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP — Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]	[PU — Public] [SEN — Sensitive] [R] [C] [S]	[month number]	[dd/mm/yyyy]
D2.1	Data about chemical and nutritional profiling of raw wastes and by products	R	PU	M14	18/04/2024
D2.2.1	On line lab-scale technical multi-device for waste processing*	Other (material)	PU	M18	25/10/2024
D2.2.2	Delivery of protocols (lab-scale) ready to scale-up the production of new high-value material (in collaboration with Companies)	R	PU	M22	16/02/2025
D2.3.1	New data about valorized matrices characterization and high value products	R	PU	M28	30/09/2025
D2.3.2	New characterized ingredients/materials for food, nutraceuticals, pharma and cosmetic applications	Other (material)	PU	M30	30/09/2025
D2.4.1	New data about sustainable production of new materials from biomasses	R	PU	M24	
D2.4.2	New characterized materials from biomasses	Other (material)	PU	M30	30/09/2025
D2.5.2	Porous sorbents from biomasses valorization	Other (material)	PU	M30	29/09/2025
D2.6.1	New material produced at pilot scale ready to the formulation or co-formulation (in collaboration with Companies)	Other (material)	PU	M32	30/09/2025
D2.6.2	New well characterized process and formulated pilot-products (in collaboration with Companies)	R/Other (Material)	PU	M32	

D2.7	Report on the adsorption and/or catalytic performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorization and non-recyclable plastic wastes	R	PU	M32	29/09/2025
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A) INTRODUCTION

The work and the outcomes reported in this Deliverable are related to the activity scheduled in Task 2.2 (focusing on Sub-Task 2.2.4). The main goal was the preparation and the characterization of porous sorbent material (derived from biomasses, exploiting different processing strategies), ready to be applied to some model of contaminants recovery (e.g. water). The activity/performances of these material will be described in another Deliverable (D2.7 “*Report on adsorption and/or catalytic performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorization and nano-recyclable plastic wastes*”).

B) ROLE OF PARTNERS

The role of the Partners involved in this activity (DiSIT-UPO and UNITO) was to identify the best performing methods to produce new porous materials from biomasses, at least at lab scale, ready to be applied on some contaminants recovery from environmental material (contaminated water or other).

C) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

Rice husk, an agricultural waste generated in large quantities worldwide and, with reference to Italy, particularly in the northern regions, was selected as waste matrix for the preparation of porous and layered inorganic materials with tuned physico-chemical properties due to its high silica content (approx. 20 wt.%). Silica extracted from rice husks has been effectively used as a more cost-effective and environmentally friendly silicon source than those normally employed in the synthesis of these materials (e.g. fumed silica, alkoxyxilanes). This silica of biogenic origin was extracted from rice hulls (supplied by a local farm in Novara (IT)) by heat treatment at 600 °C for 2 h in air (100 mL/min) in a calcination muffle furnace, resulting in the conversion of the original material into a powder (in form of ash) enriched in silicon dioxide (approx. 10-15% mass conversion). Prior to this procedure, the rice husks were thoroughly washed in water at room temperature for 30 min under vigorous stirring in order to remove dust and unwanted microparticles, then dried in an oven overnight. Afterwards, in order to remove any residual organic matter and traces of metallic impurities and thus obtain a high-purity siliceous precursor for the synthesis of the selected materials, the rice husk ashes were first submitted to a purification procedure in a mildly acidic environment (sol. 2 M HCl) at room temperature for 5 h under stirring, at the end of which the treated product was washed thoroughly with water using the Büchner filtration method and finally dried, obtaining a fine white powder.

The purified biogenic SiO_2 so-obtained was then converted into a sodium silicate solution, which was used directly for the preparation of MCM-41 and SBA-15 like ordered mesoporous silicas and, in addition, of a layered smectite-type clay called saponite. In both cases, laboratory-scale glass reactors and dedicated equipment were used during the synthetic procedures. For the mesoporous solids, this was achieved by treating the silica powder in a basic solution (approx. 1.4 M NaOH) at 70 °C for 24 h under stirring, obtaining a brownish suspension that was subsequently centrifuged (8.5k rpm for 5-10 min) to separate the aqueous silicate solution from the remaining traces of carbonaceous residues. For the rice-husk derived saponite clay, the silicate solution was obtained with the same process but using a more concentrated alkaline solution (approx. 8.5 M NaOH).

The preparation of the biogenic nanosized mesoporous MCM-41 followed the hydrothermally-assisted sol-gel procedure outlined below (Fig. 1): an appropriate amount of two organic surfactants CTABr and Pluronic F127, used to modulate the particle size and porosity of the final solid, were added to the previously prepared sodium silicate solution. The mixture was carefully stirred until the complete dissolution of the surfactants and then its pH was brought to 10 by means of multiple addition of glacial acetic acid, obtaining a white suspension. The latter was carefully stirred at room temperature for 24 h and then the resulting gel was transferred in a 100 mL sealed PTFE bottle and incubated at 60 °C for 96 h. Next, the solid was recovered through filtration, thoroughly washed with ethanol and water to removed residues of surfactants and dried at 80 °C overnight. Finally, the organic moieties were removed from the inorganic structure by calcination at 600 °C for 6 h under air flow (100 mL/min), obtaining an amount of approx. 0.9-1.0 g of nanosized porous MCM-41 powder.

Fig. 1. Synthetic steps of nanosized mesoporous MCM-41 (here labelled as RH-nanoMCM) prepared from the silica extracted from rice husks.

Biogenic mesoporous SBA-15 material was obtained using a similarly procedure, described below: initially, an appropriate amount of Pluronic P123 surfactant was dissolved in water at 30 °C for 24 h under stirring, then the resulting clear solution was transferred in a glass vessel containing the sodium silicate solution previously prepared, with the overall pH adjusted to 4 with multiple addition of glacial acetic acid. The gel that formed was transferred in 200 mL sealed PTFE bottle and incubated at 100 °C for 96 h. The solid obtained was recovered through Büchner filtration, washed with ethanol and water to removed residues of P123 and dried at 80 °C overnight. Finally, the powder was calcined at 600 °C for 6 h under air flow (100 mL/min), obtaining an amount of approx. 0.8-0.9 g of rice-husk derived SBA-15 powder.

Synthetic saponite clay prepared from the biogenic silicon source was synthesised through a modified version of the hydrothermal process (Fig. 2) previously optimised in the laboratory of DiSIT, using a starting synthesis gel with molar composition of $[\text{SiO}_2:\text{MgO}:\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Na}_2\text{O}:\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ 1:0.835:0.056:0.056:20. A final clay with high cation-exchange capacity (>100 meq/100 g) and surface acidity was obtained using this procedure. The biogenic sodium silicate solution was first mixed with appropriate amounts of magnesium acetate, aluminium isopropoxide and water and then stirred at room temperature for 2 h (manually for few minutes and then with a magnetic stir bar), after which the pH of the resulting gel was corrected to 8-9 with addition of few drops of glacial acetic acid. Next, the synthesis gel was transferred into a 125 mL acid

digestion vessel in PTFE located inside a stainless steel autoclave and heated 240 °C for 72 h. After the hydrothermal process occurred, the product was thoroughly washed with water and finally dried at 80 °C overnight, obtaining an amount of approx. 15-18 g of biogenic saponite clay.

Fig. 2. Synthetic steps of biogenic saponite clay (here labelled as SAP-R) prepared from the silica extracted from rice husks.

All the solids prepared were thoroughly characterized from a physico-chemical point-of-view using a multi-technique approach, *i.e.* X-ray powder diffraction, morphological analyses by field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) coupled with EDS elemental analyses, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), UV-Vis spectroscopy, N₂ physisorption at 77 K, ICP and CHN elemental analyses, X-ray fluorescence, FT-Infrared spectroscopy (using NH₃ and CO gaseous probes to investigate the strength and concentration of surface acid sites), solid-state NMR spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering (DLS) technique and thermogravimetry. In addition, each product obtained during the conversion of rice husks into the silicate solutions was studied in order to assess its properties, particularly in terms of SiO₂ content and purity (in the powders) and silicon speciation (in the final solutions). This information will be included in more details in the Deliverable D2.7 *“Report on adsorption and/or catalytic performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorisation and nano-recyclable plastic wastes”*.